

**COMPUTER AIDED FILAMENT WINDING USING
NON-GEODESIC TRAJECTORIES**

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ABSTRACT

Recent developments have demonstrated the integration of a 3-D computer modeller, specific applications programs and design software to produce a computer aided filament winding system. Hitherto, this process has ensured non-slippage of predicted winding trajectories by defining geodesic paths. This severely limits the choice of fibre angles comprising the structure and is an obstacle to the production of optimised composite components. This paper outlines the theory and practice of non-geodesic filament winding and demonstrates the integration of this advance into the computer aided filament winding process. Current developments in the use of thermoplastic composites and in winding non-axisymmetric shapes are described.

INTRODUCTION

The highly anisotropic nature of unidirectional fibre composites demands that for optimum performance the fibres must be correctly aligned with respect to the applied in-service loads. For this reason filament winding, in which polymer impregnated fibres are drawn onto a rotating mandrel, has become widely used for fabricating high quality composite structures since it allows continuous fibre to be placed with a high, and reproducible, degree of precision [1].

Current work on developing computer aided filament winding has resulted in a system which integrates a 3-D surface modeller, specific filament winding software, lamination theory programs, and a finite element (F.E.) analysis package. This approach, which is an attempt to produce a CAD/CAM system specific to filament winding, has been given the working name

of CADMAC, standing for Computer Aided Design and Manufacture of Advanced Composites.

THE DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING PROCESS

A flowchart of the whole design and manufacturing system as currently implemented is shown in Figure 1. While the surface modeller and F.E. packages are capable of dealing with non-axisymmetric shapes the stage at which wall thickness predictions are made is relevant, at present, only to axisymmetric shapes. However, within this limitation the complete CADMAC process has been validated for two demonstration components; a glass fibre reinforced plastic pressure vessel and a pipeline bellows [2,3].

Important stages in the CADMAC process are briefly amplified below.

Surface Modelling Software

The CADMAC process depends upon a capability to generate and access the computer geometry of the structure under consideration. Since 3-D computer modellers are commercially available the project began by carrying out a survey of suitable modelling packages on which to base the filament winding system.

The criteria applied to the selection were probably unique to this application and were primarily: the capability to generate, display and sculpt complex, free-form surfaces in an interactive manner; the ability to interface specialist applications programs with the support of the software vendor and by using information on the internal structure of the software package; the option to run on large mainframe facilities or on smaller systems which might provide a dedicated facility; and the capability of collision detection through intersection calculation routines.

The modeller selected as satisfying the most important of the above criteria was 'Systrid' which was obtained from Battelle Laboratories, Geneva and installed on the IBM 3084Q central computer.

Filament Winding Software

Special software unique to the filament winding process has been written in-house and intimately linked to Systrid to allow the generation of slip-free winding trajectories on the surface of structures modelled with Systrid. A trajectory can be guaranteed to be slip-free provided it follows a geodesic path along the surface. A unique geodesic path can be defined by the software given the starting position and angle on any surface. In practice, restricting the winding trajectories to a geodesic severely limits the opportunity to match the fibre angles to the applied stress system since the designer only has control of the fibre orientation at the geodesic starting point. Considerations of surface friction allow significant deviations from the geodesic path to be tolerated without fibre slippage. The software now has this capability and the considerable freedom that this recent development gives to tailor the composite to the application will be outlined and demonstrated in subsequent sections.

Given the predicted winding path the software then simulates the winding process by defining successive straight lines tangential to the winding path at each point. The ends of these straight lines define, in the

Figure 1. Flowchart of the computer aided design and manufacture process.

mandrel frame of reference, the successive locations that the winding machine should position the fibre feed-eye so as to wind fibre along the specified path. At this stage intersection calculation routines can be applied to check for possible regions of feed-eye/mandrel collision or fibre snagging.

Integration with Design Codes

Once the above stage has been carried out a non-slip, collision-free winding trajectory is available. For an axisymmetric component repeating this single circuit a sufficient number of times, with correctly chosen increments of mandrel rotation in between, will provide coverage of the mandrel and a completed structure. However, since the wall thickness and fibre angle will vary from point to point it may not be clear if the finished component has the necessary properties to perform satisfactorily under service conditions. Fortunately, sufficient information is available at this stage to allow the construction of an anisotropic F.E. mesh since the software can be interrogated to output the local fibre angles and geometry. This, in turn, allows predictions of the local stiffness of the candidate structure using lamination theory and calculation of the local wall thicknesses from point to point. A conventional F.E. analysis can then be carried out by inputting the appropriate boundary conditions and applied loads to predict the detailed stress distribution to check for possible regions of overstressing and, if required, the overall compliance of the structure. The F.E. analysis which has been used in this context is PAFEC from PAFEC Ltd., Nottingham which is implemented on a VAX 11/780. If the predicted performance of the candidate structure is found to be unsatisfactory, then such winding parameters as wall thickness, winding angle, fibre type or even mandrel geometry can be altered and the iterative process repeated. This is the basis of the design loop shown schematically in Figure 1. While this iterative process has many stages, since they are all computer based the design loop can be quickly traversed resulting in a structure which simultaneously satisfies the requirements of engineering design and manufacturing feasibility.

Winding Machine Control

Once an acceptable winding circuit has been defined the successive feed-eye locations are converted from the mandrel frame of reference to a co-ordinate system which corresponds to the kinematics of the winding machine. The axes currently used by CADMAC on a Baer WSE II computer controlled winding machine are; mandrel rotation, carriage translation and cross-feed arm motion. Machine compatible control data files are prepared which are then downloaded via a microcomputer. The program is then executed and the component automatically fabricated.

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF NON-GEODESICS

A geodesic path is the shortest distance between two sufficiently close points on a surface. Fibre wound under tension along a geodesic is stable since if it is disturbed it must lengthen and when released will again move back to the geodesic to take up the lowest energy configuration [4]. In practice, fibre wound along paths other than geodesic may be stable provided that the level of surface friction is sufficiently high. The following sections outline how non-slip, non-geodesic paths can be calculated and how this development will be incorporated into the CADMAC process.

The Mathematics of Non-Geodesics

A sideways force acts on an element of a fibre wound on a non-geodesic. For slippage not to occur this force must be balanced by a frictional force, the maximum magnitude of which will depend on the reaction on the element normal to the surface and the coefficient of friction between fibre and surface [5]. The relative magnitude of the normal reaction force, in turn, depends on the curvature of the surface along the winding path at that point. The greater the curvature, the greater the frictional force and the greater the deviation from the geodesic which can be tolerated without slippage. Figure 2 shows schematically the simple relationship between the surface curvature, the friction coefficient and the permissible curvature away from the geodesic. A routine which incorporates this relationship has been integrated within the filament winding software which, given a constant of friction, will define a trajectory with a constant resistance to slippage on any surface. Provided the constant of friction inputted is less than the effective coefficient of friction between fibre and mandrel the trajectory will be non-slip.

Figure 2. Schematic of the relationship between surface and trajectory curvatures and the friction coefficient.

Wall Thickness Predictions

The local wall thickness of a filament wound, rotationally symmetric structure will depend on the local diameter, tow cross-sectional area, number of circuits, and the local fibre angle. The prediction of wall thickness for a rotationally symmetric structure wound using geodesics is relatively straightforward since local fibre angle and local diameter are directly linked through Clairaut's relationship [3]. For non-geodesic winding the Clairaut relationship is not applicable and wall thickness is predicted by interrogating the software to output separately the local fibre angles and mandrel diameters.

This supplies the information required to assemble the F.E. mesh and provides the necessary link in the CADMAC design flowchart, Figure 1.

PRODUCTION OF A DEMONSTRATION CONICAL STRUCTURE

A conical structure was chosen as a suitable demonstrator of the utility of non-geodesic winding since it is a simple shape and did not introduce problems of mandrel removal or winding collisions.

Surface Modelling

The axisymmetric mandrel model was easily produced within Systrid by applying the surface of revolution action to a set of curves defining the profile as shown in Figure 3. The mandrel was then turned in the conventional way from Dural round stock.

Figure 3. Profile of the conical mandrel.

Normally, domes are machined at each end of the mandrel to facilitate fibre turnaround but in this case in order to simplify mandrel manufacture the non-geodesic capability was used to effect a turnaround on the cylindrical extensions at either end.

Path Generation

Two different winding trajectories were generated, one geodesic and the other non-geodesic on the cone portion of the mandrel. Both trajectories had the starting condition of 45° at the origin of the mandrel (shown in Figure 3) and were geodesic on the cylinder until the beginning of the cone, giving a constant angle of 45° . At the beginning of the cone one trajectory was continued as a geodesic and the winding angle increased up to 90° while still on the cone and returned back to the origin. Therefore, it is seen that coverage of the whole mandrel is impossible with a geodesic trajectory if an angle of 45° is specified at the large diameter. The winding circuit was completed by using a non-geodesic turnaround (with an inputted constant of friction of 0.2) on the waste portion of the mandrel.

In contrast, the second trajectory was non-geodesic on the cone with an inputted constant of friction of 0.215. This gave an approximately constant angle of 45° along the whole length of the cone. On the small diameter cylinder the trajectory again reverted to a geodesic and in common with the first trajectory non-geodesic turnarounds (using a constant of friction of 0.2) were effected on the waste portions of the mandrel.

Winding Simulation

Figures 4 and 5 show respectively the winding simulations corresponding to the geodesic and non-geodesic cone trajectories. The offset distance of feed-eye to mandrel was kept constant at 75 mm in both cases.

Figure 4. Winding simulation of geodesic trajectory on the cone.

Figure 5. Winding simulation of non-geodesic trajectory on the cone.

Fabrication

After downloading the numerical control instructions and correctly positioning the mandrel in the winding machine the programs were executed and the two cones fabricated using Toray, T300, 6000 filament high strength carbon fibre impregnated with MY750, HY917, DY062 Ciba-Geigy epoxide resin. No evidence of fibre slippage could be observed during winding indicating that the effective friction coefficient for this fibre/resin/mandrel combination was greater than the maximum constant of friction (0.215) used in the non-geodesic trajectory calculation.

The finished cones, with the waste portions removed, are shown together with the mandrel in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The conical mandrel with the geodesic and non-geodesic cones.

FRICITION COEFFICIENT MEASUREMENTS

In parallel with the cone modelling and fabrications independent measurements of the effective friction coefficients were carried out to explore the maximum permissible values to be used in the non-geodesic routine.

Slippage Point Measurements on Elliptical Mandrel

In reference 5 measurements of friction coefficient are described which identified the point of slippage of a circumferential wind on a spherical mandrel. The same approach was used to measure friction coefficients for the materials employed in this study, but in this case an elliptical profile mandrel was used so as to increase the horizontal separation of the likely points of slippage and increase accuracy.

Figure 7 shows how hoop fibre was progressively wound along the major axis of the mandrel until it was observed to slip. The circumferential lines indicate gradients of 0.15 to 0.40 in steps of 0.01. A video camera was used to record each experiment and the tape was subsequently played back frame by frame to observe the slippage point. In this way values of friction coefficient could be obtained even for high speed winding.

Figure 7. Friction coefficient measurements on the elliptical mandrel.

Experiments were carried out using the fibre and resin employed in fabricating the cones. The results are tabulated below.

Mandrel Surface Treatment	Fibre Resin Impregnation	Friction Coefficient	
		Initial	Final
None	Dry	0.24	0.25
PTFE Spray	Dry	0.39	0.39
PTFE Spray	Wet	0.29	0.37

Winding was carried out with a constant fibre tension of 1.5 kg and the mandrel velocity was varied systematically from 10 to 60 revs/min. No effect of winding speed was observed. The initial and final measured friction coefficients correspond respectively to gradients at which the fibre began to slip and where it became unstable on the mandrel. For fibre wound dry the slippage was catastrophic, as reflected in the similarity of the initial and final measured friction coefficients. With resin impregnated fibre the slippage was much more gradual with the quoted friction coefficients being rather approximate, subjective measurements. Work is continuing in order to clarify this behaviour and also to define the friction coefficients for fibre wound over a previous layer of composite. A surprising result was the measured increase in dry fibre friction coefficient on spraying the mandrel with PTFE. This was attributed to an increased surface roughness due to the adherence of minute globules of PTFE.

CURRENT DEVELOPMENTS

Present work is aimed at developments in software and manufacturing techniques which will allow greater design freedom in filament winding with optimised fibre angles and in manufacturing more complex shaped components.

Thermoplastic Composite Winding

In contrast to thermoset polymers, thermoplastics can be repeatedly melted, formed and resolidified. In addition to their attractive materials properties thermoplastic matrix composites offer some processing advantages over thermoset materials. In the context of filament winding, recent work has aimed to develop a thermoplastic winding head capable of taking cold, thermoplastic impregnated fibre tow, rapidly melting and deploying it onto a cold mandrel in a continuous manner. Many different methods of heating have been suggested [6] to obtain fusion of the composite including: infra-red lamps, lasers, microwaves, induction, hot iron contact, ultrasonic welding, flames and hot gas. The present approach has been to develop a simple, compact system which could be 'bolted-on' to a conventional winding machine. For this reason, a 'hot gas gun' system is under development which requires only a 4 kW electricity supply and a non-oxidising gas input. The device has been partially proved by fabricating a range of structures in glass/polyamide, glass/polypropylene and carbon/PEEK.

The fact that this method of thermoplastic winding is a continuous welding operation leads to two significant processing advantages. Firstly, since each element of the tow adheres to the composite beneath, the effective friction coefficient is very large, giving great freedom to the

designer to choose the ideal fibre paths using highly non-geodesic trajectories. Secondly, by using a correctly designed consolidation system the composite can be pressed into locally concave surfaces which would normally produce fibre bridging. Figure 8 shows a re-entrant shape hoop-wound in this way using glass/polypropylene.

Figure 8. Thermoplastic matrix composite wound into a locally concave surface.

Non-Axisymmetric Winding

Coverage of rotationally symmetric shapes is achieved by repeating a single circuit a sufficient number of times with appropriate increments of mandrel rotation. For non-rotationally symmetric shapes the concept of circuit has little meaning. One approach to achieving coverage on such shapes has been to employ CADMAC to generate many unique winding trajectories and to link these into a single winding campaign. The non-geodesic capability will be utilised to allow trajectories with different starting conditions to remain parallel over a non-axisymmetric shape, within the constraints of the appropriate friction coefficient. Figure 9 shows a conceptual design of aerogenerator blade in which a friction coefficient of 0.2 has been applied to steer a winding trajectory from a starting angle of 45° at the base to an angle of 20° at the tip.

SUMMARY

The integration into the CADMAC process of a capability for prediction of non-geodesic winding trajectories has been described and demonstrated. The theoretical aspects of non-geodesics have been outlined together with practical measurements of friction coefficient and production of two

Figure 9. Non-geodesic trajectory on a conceptual aerogenerator blade.

demonstration components. The advantages and application of thermoplastic matrix composites for filament winding have been described together with the current approaches to the production of non-axisymmetric structures.

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REFERENCES

1. Bowen, D.H., Filament winding in the 1980's, Fibre Reinforced Composites '84, University of Liverpool, 3-5th April 1984.
2. Eckold, G.C. and Wells, G.M., Computer aided design and manufacture of advanced composites, Materials Engineering Conference, London, 5-7th Nov. 1985.
3. Wells, G.M. and Eckold, G.C., Computer aided design and manufacture of filament wound composite structures, 1st Int. Conf. on Automated Composites, University of Nottingham, 10-12 Sept. 1986.

4. Lynsternik, L.A., Shortest paths: Variational problems, Survey of recent East European mathematical literature, Pergamon Press, 1964.
5. Menges, G., Wodicka, R. and Barking, H.L., Non-geodesic winding on a surface of revolution, 33rd Ann. Tech. Conf. of the Reinforced Plastics/ Composites Inst., S.P.I., 1978.
6. Tisne, J.L. and Bouvard, J., Winding with thermoplastic polymers, Proc. Third European Symp. on Spacecraft Materials in Space Environment, Noordwijk, The Netherlands, 1-4th Oct. 1985.